

Mechanistic investigation of oxidation of atenolol by *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide in alkaline medium : a kinetic approach

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Kinetic studies of the oxidation of atenolol (ATN) by sodium *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide or chloramine-T (CAT) in presence of NaOH at $26.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ follows the rate law $-d[\text{CAT}]/dt = k[\text{CAT}][\text{ATN}]^x[\text{OH}]^{-y}$, where x and y are less than unity. The variation of ionic strength and addition of the reaction product, *p*-toluenesulfonamide and Cl^- ion had no pronounced effect on the reaction rate. Decrease of dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the MeOH content decreased the rate. Composite activation parameters for the reaction have been computed from Arrhenius plot. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics is observed and activation parameters for rate limiting step have been computed. Formation and decomposition constants of CAT-ATN complexes in the reaction scheme have been determined. The conjugate acid, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NHCl}$ is assumed to be the reactive species. 4-Acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid and isopropyl amine were found to be the main oxidation products of atenolol. The proposed mechanism and derived rate law are consistent with the observed kinetic data.

Atenolol [ATN; 4-{2-hydroxy-3-[(1-methylethyl)-amino]propoxy}benzeneacetamide] is a most potent and popular drug used for its cardio selectivity action as a beta blocker and brings about the regulation of the blood pressure¹. Hence, atenolol finds extensive applications in pharmaceutical industries. It is noted that despite the importance of this drug, there seems to be no other report in the literature except from Mulla *et al.*² on the oxidation kinetics of atenolol. It was therefore, found to be of interest to investigate the mechanism of oxidation of this drug with halogen +1 oxidant. The diverse nature of the chemistry of aromatic sulfonylhaloamines is due to their ability to act as sources of halonium cations, hypohalite species and *N*-anions, which act as both bases and nucleophiles. As a result, these reagents react with a wide range of functional groups affecting an array of molecular transformation³. Sodium *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulfonamide, well known as chloramine-T (CAT) is a very important member of this class of compounds and is a by-product of saccharin manufacture. Chloramine-T contains a positive halogen and behaves as an oxidizing/chlorinating agent in both acidic and alkaline media, with a two-electron change per mole, giving *p*-toluenesulfonamide (PTS) and NaCl. The N-Cl bond in CAT is highly polar and hence this compound is a fairly strong electrophile, since chlorine leaves as Cl^+ in reactions. The oxidation

potential of CAT-PTS system is 1.138, 0.778, 0.614 and 0.500 V at pH 0.65, 7.00, 9.70 and 12.0 respectively. Mechanistic aspects of many of CAT reactions have been well documented³. However, there is meagre information in the literature on the oxidation kinetics of pharmaceuticals with CAT. Hence, it was found important and interesting to investigate the title reaction. Therefore, in the present communication, we report our investigations of the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation of atenolol by chloramine-T in aqueous alkaline medium.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of atenolol by CAT was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants in NaOH medium.

Effect of reactants : Under pseudo-first order conditions of $[\text{ATN}]_0 \gg [\text{CAT}]_0$ at constant $[\text{NaOH}]$ and temperature, plots of $\log [\text{CAT}]$ vs time were linear ($r > 0.9896$) indicating first order dependence of rate on $[\text{CAT}]_0$. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k') was unaffected by the variation in $[\text{CAT}]_0$ (Table 1), confirming the first order dependence on $[\text{CAT}]_0$. Values of k' increased with increase in $[\text{ATN}]_0$ (Table 1) and the plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [\text{ATN}]$ was linear ($r = 0.9978$) with a slope of 0.50 indicating fractional order dependence of rate on $[\text{ATN}]_0$.

Table 1. Effect of varying concentrations of oxidant, substrate and alkali on the rate of reaction at $26.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

$10^4 [\text{CAT}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{ATN}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{NaOH}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k'$ s ⁻¹
4.0	5.0	1.0	6.42
6.0	5.0	1.0	6.40
8.0	5.0	1.0	6.60
10.0	5.0	1.0	6.50
6.0	2.0	1.0	3.53
6.0	5.0	1.0	6.40
6.0	10.0	1.0	8.12
6.0	20.0	1.0	13.6
6.0	40.0	1.0	19.2
6.0	5.0	0.5	8.31
6.0	5.0	1.0	6.40
6.0	5.0	2.0	3.87
6.0	5.0	4.0	2.92
6.0	5.0	8.0	1.47
6.0	5.0	10.0	0.77

Effect of alkali : The rate decreased with increase in $[\text{NaOH}]$ (Table 1) and a plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [\text{NaOH}]$ was linear ($r = 0.9946$) with a slope of -0.60 indicating inverse fractional order dependence of rate on $[\text{NaOH}]$.

Effect of *p*-toluenesulfonamide and chloride ion : Addition of reaction product, *p*-toluenesulfonamide (ArSO_2NH_2 ; $1.0 \times 10^{-3} - 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) and Cl^- ion in the form of NaCl ($2.0 \times 10^{-2} - 8.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³) had no significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Effect of ionic strength : There was no remarkable effect on the rate of the reaction at 0.40 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength of the medium (by adding NaClO_4 solution). Hence no attempt was made to keep the ionic strength of the system constant for kinetic runs.

Effect of dielectric constant : Addition of methanol to the reaction mixture (0–30% v/v) decreased the rate (Table 2) and the plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/D$ gave a straight line ($r = 0.9920$) with a negative slope. Blank experiments showed that oxidation of methanol by CAT during the experimental period was negligible.

Solvent isotope studies : As the rate was dependent on $[\text{OH}^-]$, solvent isotope studies were made using D_2O as the solvent medium. The values of k' (H_2O) is 6.40×10^{-4} s⁻¹ and that of k' (D_2O) is 5.32×10^{-4} s⁻¹ leading to solvent isotope effect $k'(\text{H}_2\text{O}) / k'(\text{D}_2\text{O}) = 1.20$.

Test for free radicals : Addition of acrylamide solution to the reaction mixture did not initiate polymerization of the latter indicating the absence of free radical

Table 2. Effect of varying dielectric constant (D) of medium on the rate of reaction at $26.0 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

$[\text{CAT}]_0 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm ⁻³ , $[\text{ATN}]_0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³ , $[\text{NaOH}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³		
% MeOH v/v	D	$10^4 k'$ s ⁻¹
0	76.73	6.40
10	72.37	3.42
20	67.48	2.28
30	62.71	0.94

formation in the reaction sequence.

The existence of similar equilibria in acid and alkaline solutions of *N*-metallo-*N*-haloarylsulfonamide have been reported by Pryde and Soper⁴, Morris *et al.*⁵, Bishop and Jennings⁶, Higuchi *et al.*⁷ and Hardy and Johnston⁸. Chloramine-T behaves as a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions forming different species as shown in eqs. (1–6) :

Here, $\text{Ar} = \text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$

Therefore, the possible oxidation species in acid medium are the conjugate free acid (ArSO_2NHCl), dichloramine-T ($\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}_2$), hypochlorous acid (HOCl) and possibly H_2OCl^+ and in alkaline solutions ArSO_2NHCl , HOCl , $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}^-$ and OCl^- . The oxidation potential of haloaminesulfonamide system is pH dependent and decreases with increase in pH of the medium. In alkaline solutions of CAT, $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}_2$ does not exist at higher alkaline concentrations⁶. In very dilute alkali concentrations ($\text{pH} < 11$) the most likely reactive species⁸ of CAT is ArSO_2NHCl . Further, several workers^{7–9} have observed the retarding influence of OH^- ions on the rate of CAT reactions and have been attributed to the formation of the conjugate acid ArSO_2NHCl from $\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}^-$ in base retarding step. Similarly, in present investigations, the negligible influence of added *p*-toluenesulfonamide on the rate suggests that ArSO_2NHCl is the most probable oxidizing species in weak alkaline solutions of CAT. A fractional order dependence of rate on $[\text{ATN}]_0$ indicates a

pre-equilibrium before the rate-limiting step. Bearing these facts in mind, the following mechanism (Scheme 1) is proposed to account the observed kinetics :

Scheme 1

In Scheme 1, X and X' represent the complex intermediate species whose structures are shown in Scheme 2 where a detailed mechanistic interpretation of ATN oxidation

by CAT in alkaline medium is proposed.

Atenolol with 4 moles of CAT in alkaline medium gets oxidized to isopropyl amine and 4-acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid. The secondary OH group of the substrate readily reacts with one mole of the oxidant (ArSO₂NHCl) to give the intermediate complex (X, its respective oxychloride). This complex readily loses a molecule of HCl to give another intermediate complex (X', β-amino ketone). The amino group of X' reacts with another mole of oxidant to give N-haloamine. This in presence of base loses HCl to give α-amino ketone, which readily gets hydrolyzed to give isopropyl amine and α-ketaldehyde. Further, the aldehyde group of α-ketaldehyde reacts with another mole of oxidant to give α-ketocarboxylic acid. These α-ketocarboxylic acids being highly reactive, reaction with another mole of oxidant

Scheme 2. Oxidation of atenolol by CAT.

takes place readily to give the product 4-acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid by the elimination of a molecule of CO₂.

If [CAT]_t represents the total CAT concentration in solution, then

$$[\text{CAT}]_t = [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}^-] + [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NHCl}] + [\text{X}] \quad (7)$$

From step (i) and (iii), of Scheme 1

$$[\text{ArSO}_2\text{NCl}^-] = \frac{[\text{X}][\text{OH}^-]}{K_1 K_2 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}$$

$$\text{and } [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NHCl}] = \frac{[\text{X}]}{K_2 [\text{S}]}$$

Substituting these in the eq. (7) and solving for [X], we get

$$[\text{X}] = \frac{K_1 K_2 [\text{CAT}]_t [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (8)$$

Step (iii) of Scheme 1 determines the overall rate

$$\text{Rate} = -d[\text{CAT}]_t/dt = k_3[\text{X}] \quad (9)$$

By substituting for [X] from eq. (8) in eq. (9), following rate law (10) is obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{CAT}]_t [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

Rate law (10) is in good agreement with all experimental results. Since rate = *k'* [CAT]_t, rate law (10) can be transformed into eqs. (11) to (13) :

$$k' = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{ATN}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} + \frac{1}{K_2 k_3 [\text{ATN}]} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{K_2 k_3 [\text{ATN}]} \left\{ \frac{[\text{OH}^-]}{K_1 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} + 1 \right\} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (13)$$

From the slopes and intercepts of the linear double reciprocal plots of 1/*k'* vs 1/[ATN] (*r* = 0.9719) at fixed [OH⁻] and 1/*k'* vs [OH⁻] (*r* = 0.9948) at constant [ATN], values of formation constants (*K*₁ and *K*₂) and decompo-

sition constant (*k*₃) for the standard run at 26 ± 0.1°C found were 6.8 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ and 6.1 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³, 434 dm³ mol⁻¹ and 18.2 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ respectively. Further, the values of *K*₁ obtained from both the plots are comparable. Therefore, the near constancy of *K*₁ forms a strong evidence for the formation of the species ArSO₂NHCl from ArSO₂NCl⁻ and H₂O [step (i) of Scheme 1] for the oxidation of ATN by CAT in alkaline medium.

Since the rate was fractional order in [ATN]₀, Michaelis-Menten kinetics¹⁰ were adopted to study effect of [ATN]₀ on the rate at different temperatures (20–40°C). The decomposition constants *k*₃ [step (iii) of Scheme 1] were calculated at different temperatures using eq. (13). Using these *k*₃ values, activation parameters for the rate limiting step were determined from the linear Arrhenius plot of log *k*₃ vs 1/*T* (*r* = 0.9990). These data are compiled in Table 3.

Table 3. Values of decomposition constants (*k*₃) and activation parameters for the rate limiting step

Temp. °C	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₃ s ⁻¹	Activation parameters	
20.0	10.0	<i>E</i> _a kJ mol ⁻¹	62.9
26.0	18.2	Δ <i>H</i> [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	60.4
30.0	25.0	Δ <i>S</i> [‡] JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	-95.9
40.0	55.5	Δ <i>G</i> [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	89.3

A change in the solvent composition by varying the methanol content in methanol-water affects the reaction rate. The general equation relating to the effect of dielectric constant to the reaction velocity in a bimolecular reaction has been derived by Landskroener and Laidler¹¹. For the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles, Amis¹² has shown that

$$\ln k'_D = \ln k'_{D=\infty} - 2 \mu_1 \mu_2 / DkTr^3 \quad (14)$$

where *k*'_D is a function of dielectric constant *D*, μ₁ and μ₂ are the dipole moments of reactions, *r* is the distance of approach for the two dipoles, *k* is the Boltzmann constant and *T* is the absolute temperature. Eq. (14) predicts a linear relation between log *k'* and 1/*D*. The slope of the line should be negative for a reaction between two dipole molecules and positive for ion-dipole reactions. In present case, the plot of log *k'* vs 1/*D* is linear with a negative slope, thus supporting the participation of two dipole species in the rate limiting step.

The observed solvent isotope effect supports the proposed mechanism and the derived rate law. For a reaction involving a fast equilibrium H^+ or OH^- ion transfer, the rate increases in D_2O medium since D_3O^+ and OD^- are stronger acid and stronger base, respectively, than H^+ and OH^- ions¹³. In the present case, the observed solvent isotope effect of $k'(H_2O)/k'(D_2O) > 1$ is due to the greater basicity of OD^- compared to OH^- . However, the magnitude of retardation in D_2O is small (expected value is 2 to 3 times greater¹³) due to the hydrolysis step, which tends to make the normal kinetic isotope effect $k_H/k_D > 1$ for the slow step of Scheme 1, and also fractional negative order dependence on $[OH^-]$.

The mechanism is further supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and the other thermodynamic parameters. The fairly high positive values of free energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicates that the transition state is highly solvated, while the large negative entropy of activation suggests the formation of the compact activated complex with fewer degrees of freedom. The reduction product ($ArSO_2NH_2$) does not influence the rate, showing that it is not involved in pre-equilibrium. Change in the ionic strength of the medium does not alter the rate indicating that non-ionic species are involved in the rate limiting step. Addition of Cl^- ion has no effect on the rate indicating that no free chlorine is formed in the reaction. All these observations also confirm the proposed mechanism and derived rate law.

Experimental

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified by the method of Morris *et al.*⁵. An aqueous solution of the compound was standardized by the iodometric method and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration. Atenolol (Aldrich) was used without further purification. Aqueous solutions of desired strength were prepared prior to use. Heavy water (D_2O , 99.4%) was supplied by the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India. Permittivity (dielectric constant, D) of the reaction medium was altered by the addition of methanol in varying proportions (v/v) and values of permittivity for methanol-water mixtures reported¹⁴ in literature were employed. No attempt was made to keep the ionic strength of the system constant since the pseudo-first order rate constant remains unaltered in presence of $0.40 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} NaClO_4$ solution. All other chemicals employed were of accepted grades of purity. Double distilled water was used throughout these kinetic reactions.

Kinetic measurements : The rate studies were made

under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of atenolol over CAT. Solutions containing appropriate amounts of substrate, acid and water (to keep the total volume constant for all runs) were taken in a glass stoppered Pyrex boiling tube and thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$ for thermal equilibrium. A measured amount of CAT solution, also thermostated at the same temperature, was added to the mixture. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of unreacted CAT in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time. The course of reaction was studied for two half-lives. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k') were evaluated from $\log [CAT]$ vs time plots were reproducible within $\pm 3-4\%$. Regression analysis of the experimental data to obtain regression coefficient (r) was performed with an fx-100W scientific calculator.

Stoichiometry : Varying ratios of CAT to ATN in presence of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} NaOH$ equilibrated at $26.0^\circ C$ for 24 h. The unreacted CAT in reaction mixture was determined by iodometric titration. The analysis showed that one mole of atenolol reacted with four moles of CAT and the observed reaction stoichiometry is represented as :

Product analysis : One of the reaction products, *p*-toluenesulfonamide ($ArSO_2NH_2$) was identified by paper chromatography¹⁵. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl in ethanol as spray reagent ($R_f = 0.905$). The oxidation product of atenolol was found to be 4-acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid, isopropyl amine and CO_2 . 4-Acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid was separated as solid and it was filtered and recrystallized by alcohol. It was identified by IR spectrum, which showed a band at 1662 cm^{-1} due to $>C=O$ stretching and a band at 3043 cm^{-1} due to $O-H$ stretching. Two bands were observed at 3359 cm^{-1} and 3266 cm^{-1} for $-NH_2$ and also a $>C=O$ band at 1641 cm^{-1} . The other oxidation product, isopropyl amine was detected by spot test¹⁶. The evolved CO_2 was detected by lime water test. It was observed that the 4-acetamido-benzene-oxy-acetic acid and isopropyl amine do not undergo further oxidation under the present kinetic conditions.

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